

Fluorescence quantum yield of N-[4-(benzothiazol-2-yl)phenyl]-octanamide BPO

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Methodology

All the chemicals used in the experiment are commercially available and were therefore commercially acquired. The absorption criteria were recorded using Hitachi U-3010 spectrophotometer and the Hitachi F-700 fluorescence spectrophotometer used to record fluorescence emission spectra. The H-NMR was used to characterize chemical structures of the chemicals and the Hamamatsu Quantaurs spectrometer used to determine fluorescence quantum yields.

A solution of known concentration was prepared.

A drop of HCl was added to the solution to form an open ring

The sample was then subjected to UV spectrum with a molar absorption coefficient of 7053.2 M⁻¹cm⁻¹ at 365 nm.

A drop of triethylammina was then added to ensure the results form an open ring

The solution was then subjected to a radiation of 470nm. The 437 nm peak dropped and anew peak of 330nm with molar mass absorption coefficient of 753.5 M⁻¹cm⁻¹ at 365nm.

The nanoparticles were prepared through injection of μL THF of 10^{-3}mol L^{-1} BPO into 10mL ddH₂O and stirred vigorously for 3 seconds at room temperature. The samples were then subjected to UV-vis absorption and fluorecence measurements.

The dry dopped PMMA films were prepared by dissolving BPO/PMMA at a aratio of 1:100,w/w into dicloromethane. The solution obtained was applied on to commercial UV-LED set to obtain a covered film for light demonstration.

Results and Discussion

The N-[4-(benzothiazol-2-yl)phenyl]-octanamide BPO was syntehezied by condensing aminobenzoic acid with aminobenzenethiol. It was then subjected to amidation using n-caprylic acid. The compound is soluble in common organic solvents including chloroform and hydroxyl but not in water as it has no hydroxyl group as the main reason for the difference in photophysical properties with similar compounds in the same family.

The absorption and emission spectrum of the BPO solution in THF and the aqueous suspension of their corresponding nano particles lie in the UV region implying that both dilute and nano particles of the compound are colorless. When subjected to excitation at the 365 nm light, the BPO solution in THF and the aqueous suspension of its nanoparticles show a range of emission

properties. The emission maximum of the BPO in THF solution locates at UV region. The nano particle suspension of the compound shows a blue-violet emission with a maximum of 425 nm and a 0.124 fluorescence quantum yield owing to the enlarged π -electron conjugation in aggregates.

The Quantum yield calculation

$$Q_S = Q_R \times I_s/I_r \times A_r/A_s \times n_s^2/n_r^2$$

Q_S = quantum yield of the sample, Q_R = quantum yield of the reference, I_s =area under the PL curve of the sample, I_r =area under the PL curve of the reference, A_r = absorbance of the reference, A_s = absorbance of the sample, n_s =refractive index of the sample, n_r = refractive index of reference.